

EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT ON CONDUCTIVITY OF DOPED POLY(ANILINE) (PANI)/GRAPHENE OXIDE (GO) COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The composite prepared from polyaniline (PANI) doped with dodecyl benzene sulfonic acid (DBSA) and graphene oxide (GO) is expected to be a new transparent conductive material due to the electronic interaction between them. The PANI/GO thin film composite with 50 wt% GO ($GO/(GO+PANI)=0.5$) heat-treated over 150 °C for 1 hour in the air exhibited much higher conductivity than PANI and GO respectively (PANI/GO: $3.2 \times 10^{-2} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, PANI: $4.1 \times 10 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, GO: $3.6 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$). Therefore the effects of GO (or PANI) content and heat-treatment temperature on the conductivity of PANI/GO thin film composites were studied in detail. The conductivity of PANI/GO thin film composites increased with PANI content and heat-treatment temperature. Measurements of UV-VIS spectra and zeta-potential of PANI/GO/water dispersion suggested the presence of chemical and physical interaction between PANI and GO in the dispersion. However the conductivity enhancement of PANI/GO thin film composites is due not to such interaction, but to DBSA contained as a dopant in PANI, which promotes the reduction of GO to rGO (reduced type GO) with more C=C(sp²) bond at a higher temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polyaniline (PANI) doped with an acid like dodecyl benzene sulfonic acid (DBSA) is one of the conductive polymers which are expected to be promising materials taking the place of a conventional transparent conductive material, Sn-doped In₂O₃ (ITO), since PANI possesses good conductivity, transparency and environmental stability. However the conductivity of PANI must be too low to take the place of ITO. So there are many studies on the improvement of its conductivity by the use of additives or modification of dopant [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Doped polyaniline (PANI)

Dopant: dodecylbenzene sulfonic acid (DBSA)

Figure 1: Chemical structures of PANI and DBSA

On the other hand graphene (Gr) shown in Fig.1 is a giant aromatic poly-molecule having high electrical conductivity, mechanical strength and optical absorption properties. It can be incorporated into organic polymers to enhance electrical conductivity and mechanical strength. So Gr is a promising material taking the place of ITO. Gr monolayer is provided by exfoliation of graphite with “Scotch tape” method [6], but its yield is very low. Then Gr is generally produced by the reduction of graphene oxide (GO) produced by the oxidation of graphite particles [7]. The conductivity of resulting GO is much lower than that of graphite, since the surface of GO has lots of OH, COOH and epoxy groups as shown in Fig.1 [8], but GO has a good dispersibility in the aqueous solution and hydrophilic polymers.

Figure 2: Synthetic diagram of GO, rGO and Gr

Since GO (or reduced GO (rGO)) and PANI have benzene rings, OH, COOH and –NH– groups there are expected to be interactions such as π - π stacking and hydrogen bonding between GO (or rGO) and PANI in the solid mixture (composite) of PANI and GO, which possibly causes the formation of longer and denser conductive networks in the PANI/GO composites. So PANI/GO (or rGO) has a possibility to show higher conductivity than PANI and GO themselves. There was a study on the conductive composites of PANI and graphite [9], but not the conductive composites of PANI and GO (or rGO). Then the authors have been studying the conductivity of PANI/GO in order to get higher conductivity and transparency.

In this paper the effect of GO (or PANI) content and heat-treatment on the conductivity of PANI/GO composite will be discussed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

GO/water dispersion (conc.; 1.0 wt%) was purchased from Nishina Material company in Okayama University in Japan. The aqueous PANI/water dispersion (conc.: 5.0 wt%) was purchased from Kakensangyo Co., Ltd in Japan. Dodecyl benzene sulfonic acid (DBSA) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. LLC. Commercial pure water was used for the preparation of PANI/GO composites and measurements of zeta-potential and UV-VIS spectra of PANI/GO/water dispersion. A pre-cleaned micro slide glass with the size of 76 mm \times 26 mm and the thickness of 0.9-1.2 mm was used as a substrate for the preparation of PANI (or DBSA)/GO thin film composites.

2.2 Preparation of PANI/GO and DBSA/GO thin film composites

The mixtures of GO and PANI dispersions with the different weight ratio of GO/(GO+PANI) were dispersed with ultrasonic waves for 20 min, and a small amount of the resulting mixtures were dropped with a syringe on the slide glass. The coated slide glasses were dried under the conditions of 100, 130, 150 and 170 °C for 1.0 hour in air. The thickness (t) of the coated layer of PANI/GO composites were controlled to be around 2 μm, and calculated from the weight of the dried composites. The preparation and characterization of DBSA/GO composites with a different weight ratio of GO/(GO+DBSA) were carried out according to the above procedure.

2.3 Measurement

The particle-size and zeta-potential of GO in the dispersion with the GO concentration of 0.020~0.10wt% were measured by the use of the zeta-potential & size analyzer with a titrator, ELS-Z (Photal Otsuka electronics Co. Ltd in Japan).

The zeta potential change of GO dispersion (conc.; 0.060 %) in the presence of PANI was measured by the above ELS-Z with a titrator.

UV spectra of PANI/GO/water suspension were measured by UV spectrometry (JASCO UV-650).

Raman spectra of PANI/GO composites were measured with Raman spectroscopy (JASCO NRS-1000) under the following conditions; wave length: 532nm, output: 10mW, exposure time: 60sec.

XPS spectra of heat-treated PANI/GO, DBSA/GO and GO were measured with automated X-ray imaging photoelectron spectrometer (SHIMADZU KRATOS NOVA)

Surface resistivity (R_s , Ω/\square) of PANI or DBSA/GO thin film composites on the glass plate was measured with Lowresta (Mitsubishi Chemical Co. Ltd.) under the following condition; temperature: 20-25 °C, humidity: 45-60 %, voltage: 100 V. Volume resistivity (ρ) was calculated according to the following equation.

$$\rho (\Omega \cdot \text{cm}) = R_s (\Omega/\square) \times t (\text{cm})$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of GO particles in water

The average diameter and zeta-potential of GO particles were estimated to be 7×10^3 nm and -38 mV. The absolute value of its zeta-potential is so large that GO particles are dispersed well in water due to the coulomb repulsive force among them.

3.2 Characterization of PANI/GO dispersion mixed in water

Fig 3 shows the zeta potential change of GO particles in water in the presence of titrated PANI. The zeta-potential of GO increased with the increase of PANI, which suggests the formation of PANI/GO adduct in the mixture. Since the surface of GO has a minus charge and OH groups, GO particles adsorbed doped PANI molecules with $-\text{NH}^+=\text{C}$ (emeraldine salt) and $-\text{NH}-$ groups, which possibly resulted in the change of its zeta-potential from -38mV to -24mV. Fig.4 shows the UV spectra of the PANI/GO mixture in water. The peak at 760 nm attributable to the absorption of polaron bond in PANI shifted to the shorter wave, which was possibly caused by the partial dissociation of the dopant (DBSA) from polyaniline molecules by the added GO with OH groups. Thus it is concluded that there is some interaction between PANI molecules and GO particles in water.

Figure 3: Zeta potential of GO titrated with aqueous PANI solution

Figure 4: UV-Vis spectra of GO/PANI/water dispersion (PANI conc.: 0.06 %)

3.3 Effect of GO content on volume resistivity (ρ) of PANI/GO thin film composites

Fig.5 shows the ρ values of the PANI/GO thin film composites with the different weight ratio of GO/(GO+PANI), which were heat-treated at 100, 150 and 170 °C. The ρ value change of PANI/GO composites was dependent on the heat treatment temperature. The ρ values of PANI/GO composites heat-treated at 100 °C increased with the weight ratio of GO/(GO+PANI), while the ρ values of PANI/GO composites heat-treated at 150 and 170 °C decreased gradually with the increase of GO content, but GO thin film showed higher ρ value than PANI/GO composite. PANI/GO composites with the ratio of GO/(GO+PANI) ranging from 0.4 to 0.5 showed lower ρ value (higher conductivity) than PANI and heat-treated GO (rGO).

Figure 5: Effects of GO addition and heat treatment on ρ values of PANI/GO thin film composites (heat-treatment conditions: 100, 150, 170 °C \times 1 hour)

Fig.6 shows the Raman spectra of the PANI/GO thin film composites heat-treated at 150 °C for 1 hour. The G-band peak of the PANI/GO composites observed around 1595 cm^{-1} did not shift with the PANI content, which suggests that the electronic state of GO in the heat-treated PANI/GO is not influenced by PANI molecules, which suggests that there is no electronic interaction between GO and PANI in the heat-treated PANI/GO thin film composite.

Figure 6: Raman spectra of PANI/GO thin film composites heat-treated at 150 °C for 1 hour

Fig.7 shows the XPS spectra of the PANI/GO thin film composites heated-treated at 100, 150 and 170 °C, and the concentration of atomic bond species such as C-C(sp^3), C=C(sp^2), C-N, C-O, C=O, and COO calculated from them. The concentration of C-O bond decreases with the heat-treatment

temperature while at the same time the concentration of $C=C(sp^2)$ bond increases. There was little change of the concentration of $C-C(sp^3)$ bond. It was concluded that heat-treatment contribute to the production of $C=C(sp^2)$ bond from $C-O$ bond which results in the decrease of volume resistivity of PANI/GO thin film composites.

Figure 7: XPS spectra and bond species of PANI/GO thin film composites heat-treated at 100,150 and170 °C for 1 hour

3.4 Mechanism of heat-treatment effect on conductivity enhancement of PANI/GO composites

As mentioned above, conductivity enhancement of PANI/GO was not caused mainly by the electronic interaction such as π - π stacking between GO (or rGO) and PANI in the heat-treated PANI/GO solid, but by the increase of $C=C(sp^2)$ bond owing to the heat-treatment. There are some reports that GO sheets can be readily reduced under a mild condition using hydrohalic acid [10] or L-ascorbic acid (L-AA) [11]. It can be assumed that such conductivity enhancement is due to the thermal reduction of GO by the acid (DBSA) added in PANI as a dopant.

Fig.7 shows the relationship between the content of DBSA and volume resistivity of PANI or DBSA /GO composites heat-treated at 100, 130, 150 and 170°C. Their volume resistivity ρ values decreased with the increase of DBSA and heat treatment temperature. The ρ value change was dependent on DBSA content and a heat-treatment temperature. There is little difference in the ρ value change behavior between PANI/DBSA composites and DBSA/GO composites, in particular at over 150 °C as shown in Fig.8. It was concluded that the decrease of volume resistivity of PANI/GO thin film composites is caused by DBSA as dopant, which promote the change of GO to rGO with more $C=C(sp^2)$ bond.

Figure 8: Effect of DBSA content and heat-treatment temperature on the volume resistivity ρ of PANI/GO and DBSA/GO thin film composites

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of GO (or PANI) content and heat-treatment temperature on the conductivity of PANI/GO thin film composites were studied in detail. The conductivity of PANI/GO thin film composites increased with PANI content and heat-treatment temperature. Measurements of UV-VIS spectra and zeta-potential of PANI/GO/water dispersion disclosed the presence of chemical and physical interaction between PANI and GO in the dispersion. However the conductivity enhancement of PANI/GO thin film composites is not due to such interaction, but to DBSA contained as a dopant in PANI, which promotes the reduction of GO to rGO (reduced type GO) with more C=C(sp²) bond at a higher temperature.

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